

Employee Performance Analysis at Community Service Units in Makassar City

¹Akhmad Syaekhu, ²Umar Kamaruddin

Faculty of Social and Political Science
Universitas Sawerigading, Makassar, Indonesia

Abstract: This article describes the performance of employees at the level of middle management and low management along with various indicators. The research method is a survey with a quantitative approach involving 140 respondents. Researchers used a questionnaire instrument to capture employee performance data. The results of quantitative descriptive analysis showed that employee performance at low management levels was higher than employees at middle management level. Furthermore, the results of the statistical analysis with the ANOVA test showed that there were no differences in performance in the two management levels.

Index Terms: middle management, low management, creativity

I. INTRODUCTION

Employee performance management is an continuing activity in an organization. This activity is the part of efforts to achieve the organization goals by effectively and efficiently. Furthermore, the employee engagement is an absolute thing in organization activity [1]. Local governments as organizational units are responsible for providing services to the community. Therefore, the community service unit must show good performance and sustainable work spirit.

The performance definition in various theories is the work of employees in carrying out tasks that are measured in quality and quantity. Performance is also defined as an output of activity or productivity. Generally performance is the achievement of employee performance in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them. Furthermore, employee performance measurement includes various indicators. (table 1)

Table 1. The Description of Indicator

Indicator	Description
Creativity [2]	the employees ability to develop new ideas as problem-solving efforts.
Productivity [3]	a measure of resource utilization to achieve optimal results.
Punctuality [4] [5]	On time performance
Initiative ([6]	The ability to find work solutions independently
Communication [7]	Ability to make working relationship with othe people or other work units

Employee performance studies are carried out at all levels of management. However, middle management and low management are generally the key to success in achieving organizational goals. This study describes the employee performance at the Community Service Unit in Makassar City. Specifically this study describes the differences in employee performance at the middle management level and low management level.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research locations in 20 community service units are divided into 8 sub-district offices and 12 village offices. Respondents as research samples are described in the table 2.

Table 2. Description of Sample

No	Units	Number of Units	Management Level	Number of Respondent
1	District Office	7	Middle management	35
			Low management	35
2	Sub-district Office	7	Middle management	35
			Low management	35

Data analysis with quantitative descriptive method and different test using ANOVA method. Statistical testing is processed by using SPSS

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Employee performance is measured by five indicators, namely creativity, punctuality, productivity, initiative and communication. The description of the descriptive analysis of employee creativity shows that low management results in higher creativity than employees in middle management (figure 1).

Figure 1. Description of Employee Creativity.

The employee ability to provide community service on time is one of the performance indicators. Punctuality or the employee ability to complete tasks on time is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Description of Employee Punctuality.

Employees at low management level have the ability to complete tasks on time. Figure 2 shows that none of the employees are at a low management level which results in a very low level of work accuracy. The fact also shows that there are six employees at the middle management level who produce punctuality in the very low category.

Employee initiatives in finding solutions to the problems they faced greatly determine the produced performance. This is influenced by knowledge of problems and diverse work experience. The results of descriptive analysis of employee initiatives are presented in Figure 3

Figure 3. Description of Employee Initiatives.

Figure 3 shows that employees at low management level have higher initiatives than employees in middle management. There are even five employees in the middle management who show very low initiative.

Employees carry out organizational tasks by utilizing resources such as labor, equipment and time. Productivity as a measure of employee performance in utilizing resources. A productivity indicator is the ability to use equipment appropriately, the ability to complete work according to the promised time span and the ability to manage human resources. The results of labor productivity analysis at two management levels are presented in the figure 4.

Figure 4. Description of Employee Productivity

Employee productivity is generally in the high category. generally, employees at middle management level show lower performance than middle management employees. Communication is an important factor in achieving optimal work results. The employee ability to communicate with peers, superiors and subordinates is useful in building good cooperation in carrying out tasks. This study reviews the variables of communication in oral communication indicators, writing communication and electronic mail communication. Analysis of the ability of employees to communicate is presented in the figure 5.

Figure 5. Description of The Communication of Employee

The analysis results on the picture show that middle management employees have better communication skills. However, from 140 respondents, there were 50% of respondents who showed low and very low communication skills.

General employee performance is shown in the Figure 6.

Figure 6. Employee Performance

Figure 6 shows that most employees at the middle management level show very high performance while middle level management employees with high performance. This picture indicates that middle management employees have high morale which is marked by the completion of their work, innovation and productivity.

Statistical analysis to assess numbers per indicator at two management levels reviewed was carried out by ANOVA analysis. Statistical analysis results are shown in table 3. The results of the ANOVA test analysis show that the sig value <0.05 indicates that there is no difference in performance between the two management levels. Conversely, if the sig value > 0.05 , employees at both levels show different performance. The results of the analysis in the table 3 show that the indicators of productivity and education show the value of sig > 0.05 . These results indicate that the ability to utilize resources in middle-level employees is different from low-level employees. Likewise, communication skills in employees at the middle level differ from those of employees at low levels. In fact, differences in the ability of employees at both levels are due to mastery of technology. Middle-level employees are generally aged 50 years and over with a low level of technology mastery. The employee ability at the middle level to have low computer skills. Likewise with the mastery of the use of information technology, employees at low management levels with a relatively young age generally master information technology usage. This has led to differences in performance aspects at two levels of management

Table 3. ANOVA Analysis

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Creativity	Between Groups	5.600	1	5.600	12.351	.001
	Within Groups	62.571	138	.453		
	Total	68.171	139			
Punctuality	Between Groups	3.150	1	3.150	4.997	.027
	Within Groups	86.986	138	.630		
	Total	90.136	139			
Initiative	Between Groups	6.429	1	6.429	10.619	.001
	Within Groups	83.543	138	.605		
	Total	89.971	139			
Productivity	Between Groups	4.114	1	4.114	6.417	.012
	Within Groups	88.486	138	.641		
	Total	92.600	139			
Communication	Between Groups	.064	1	.064	.065	.799
	Within Groups	136.929	138	.992		
	Total	136.993	139			

Generally, performance changes between the two levels of management are presented in the table 4

Table 4 ANOVA Analysis Results on Performance Variables for Both Levels

ANOVA					
Performance					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.210	1	3.210	19.366	.000
Within Groups	22.877	138	.166		
Total	26.087	139			

Statistical analysis on the table .. shows the value of sig = 0.000 < 0.05 or there is no difference in the performance of the workforce at the middle level with a low level. The results show that indicators that greatly affect employee performance in both levels are communication and productivity. Workers at the middle level tend to be less motivated to produce optimal performance. This fact is related to job satisfaction and personal skills.

The previous studies revealed that personal skills is the base of employees to develop their ability. The young employees who have good satisfaction relatively have good competence. [8]. Furthermore, the motivation to develop themselves in lower level employees is also higher, while at the middle level the motivation is less visible because of the requirement to make a heavier career and smaller opportunities. This fact is in accordance with previous studies that Managers with a passion to develop a high career and want to have institutional power tends to be more effective than those who only have personal desires.[9].

In addition, the service sector requires employees with motivation to serve the public. If someone has motivation for high public services, the result performance will be better. These motivations usually develop with the presence of rewards in the form of promotions or material awards. [10]

IV. CONCLUSION

Employees at the Community Service Unit in Makassar City showed very high performance. Particularly, employees at low management levels produce higher performance than employees at the middle management level. The results of statistical analysis show that there are significant differences in two performance indicators, namely productivity and employee communication skills. This indicates that both indicators are important indicators for employee performance in service units in Makassar City.

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